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Shaping Energy for a Sustainable Future

Unlocking Versatility in Power Converter Prototyping with TyphoonHIL

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I. A rapid control prototyping approach with Typhoon HIL

When developing power converters, migrating from simulation to prototype is a key challenge. Simulation software often uses simplified models that don't fully capture the complexities of real-world systems. As a result, control algorithms developed and tested purely in simulation may not perform as expected when implemented on physical hardware. Differences in code between simulation and real controller implementation can also lead to instability, delays, or inaccurate responses in the prototype.

In the early design stages, the Typhoon HIL toolchain allows for the Model-In-the-Loop (MIL) approach, where the HIL device is used to simulate both the power stage and the controller. This means that the entire system is tested within a simulated environment where potential issues can be identified early in the design process without needing to deploy the system on physical hardware.

As development progresses, Typhoon HIL's high-performance real-time simulators enable the testing and validation of controllers in realistic scenarios using the Controller Hardware-In-the-Loop (C-HIL) approach. This methodology, central to the Typhoon HIL technology, is characterized by the high-fidelity real-time simulation of the power stage in a HIL device, while a real external controller interfaces with the system.

While MIL and C-HIL are well established within the Typhoon HIL toolchain, this whitepaper focuses on employing Typhoon HIL real-time simulators as prototype controllers by means of Rapid Control Prototyping (RCP). In this approach MIL is initially employed with both the power converter system (PCS) and its control loops implemented in the Typhoon HIL simulator, as seen in the left side of Figure 1. As the next stage, instead of transitioning to the C-HIL approach, the physical PCS prototype is developed. However, the control unit remains implemented in the Typhoon HIL simulator rather than being deployed to an external target platform. In this configuration, the HIL device works as a prototype controller, requiring minimal code modifications to interface with the physical converter hardware prototype. This methodology simplifies the workflow and provides a reliable, robust, and streamlined solution to design and test PCS control strategies.

In that regard, this document focuses on the versatility offered by Typhoon HIL simulator devices in the development of power converters, emphasizing their capabilities in simplifying and accelerating the prototyping process.

Figure 1. Migrating from simulation to system validation with Typhoon HIL.

HYBRIS project: A success case

The following sections describe the application of this approach within the [HYBRIS project](#). The HYBRIS project focuses on developing an advanced hybrid energy storage system (HESS) that combines two complementary battery technologies: Lithium Titanate (LTO) and Aqueous Organic Redox Flow Batteries (AORFB). Its main goal is to address the challenges of renewable energy integration, such as reliability and grid stability, by optimizing energy storage solutions.

As part of this initiative, the [Catalonia Institute for Energy Research \(IREC\)](#) developed the power conversion system, a critical component enabling efficient energy transfer between the batteries and the grid, as well as between the two battery technologies.

Therefore, Section II covers the optimized power conversion system architecture. Section III presents its validation using a HIL404 device for real-time simulation. Section IV details the hardware implementation, control setup, and experimental testbench with this same device. Finally, Section V demonstrates the experimental results, confirming reliable system operation and alignment with design expectations. General conclusions for the PCS prototype development with Typhoon HIL are provided in Section VI.

II. Power conversion system overview

HYBRIS's PCS was developed based on an [optimization study](#) with three primary objectives: minimizing energy losses, reducing capital costs, and minimizing costs associated with PCS reliability. The study concluded that, for the given HESS, the optimal PCS architecture consists of one dc-dc converter per battery and a single dc-ac converter. This configuration was determined to provide the best balance between cost and efficiency. Figure 2 illustrates the schematic of the optimized design.

Figure 2. Optimum PCS architecture.

Firstly, the dc-dc modules are implemented with the dual-active-bridge (DAB) converter topology seen in Figure 3. The DAB converter allows bidirectional power transfer, a high step-up and step-down voltage gain, and provides galvanic isolation, thanks to the use of a high-frequency transformer.

Figure 3. The dc-dc DAB converter topology.

Figure 4. Closed-loop control diagram of the LTO and AORF DAB converters. Variables in blue are measured with sensors in the PCS.

The DAB is operated with the conventional phase-shift modulation (PSM). The PSM synthesizes two square-wave voltages at the LV and HV bridges and the transferred power is controlled through the phase shift between both ac voltages. Besides, PSM allows for a simple implementation since it only features a single control variable. In this regard, Figure 4 schematizes the closed-loop control diagram of the dc-dc DAB converters.

Secondly, the dc-ac module is implemented with a three-phase two-level dc-ac converter, shown in Figure 5. The dc-ac converter is in charge of transferring power from the common dc-link to the utility grid, and vice versa. The dc-ac converter is operated with sinusoidal pulse-width modulation (SPWM). Figure 6 shows the closed-loop control diagram of the dc-ac converter.

Figure 5. Three-phase two-level dc-ac converter topology.

Figure 6. Closed-loop control diagram dc-ac converter. Variables in blue are measured with sensors in the PCS.

III. PCS design validation in Typhoon HIL

The HESS PCS design was validated through simulation using the Model-in-the-Loop simulation approach. In this configuration, the power stage of the PCS was run alongside the control loops in real-time simulation mode on a HIL404 device. This simulation allowed for the validation of key aspects of the PCS before proceeding to manufacturing:

- **Hardware-related aspects:** Evaluation of topology design, component selection, and performance under multiple operating conditions.
- **Software-related aspects:** Assessment of the real-time behaviour of the control loops.

Figure 7. With the MIL approach, both the power stage and the control loops run in real time in a Typhoon HIL simulator.

In this regard, the power stage was modeled using the Schematic Editor tool, which is part of the Typhoon HIL Control Center toolchain. The components used in modeling the circuit are all part of the Schematic Editor's core library, such as the Three-Phase Inverter used in the DC-AC converter stage. The DC-DC stage in the plant model is implemented using four Half Bridge components, considering the HYBRIS use case requirements.¹

Due to the size of the converter, the model was divided into three separate cores connected via Core Coupling links. Figure 8 shows screenshots of the PCS electrical model.

On the other hand, the control loops were implemented using components from the core library, specifically the Signal Processing library, which contains components for both control loop and non-electrical-domain modelling, such as functions, mathematical operations, and logical operations, among others.

¹ [In applications requiring higher switching frequencies, DAB topologies can be implemented using a dedicated DC-DC converter solver for increased fidelity.](#)

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Electrical model of the converters for real-time simulations. (a) dc-dc DAB converters. (b) dc-ac converter.

The main difference in implementation compared to the schematics in Figure 4 and Figure 6 is the absence of a modulator, as the component blocks that simulate the converters have embedded PWM modulators that employ duty cycle values as inputs. The control loops block diagrams for the DAB converters and the dc-ac converter are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Closed-loop control implementation for the converters simulation. (a) LTO battery dc-dc DAB converter (analogous for the AORF battery dc-dc DAB converter). (b) dc-ac converter.

Once the electrical model and control loops were implemented, the converter design was validated via the MIL approach, addressing the key aspects stated beforehand.

In that regard, Figure 10 shows the current and voltage waveforms for the DAB converters and the dc-ac converter. These waveforms were captured with the Capture/Scope widget in HIL SCADA. The DAB waveform at both converters show the expected evolution. Besides, the regulation of the dc-link voltage performs as desired with a minimal voltage ripple.

Figure 10. HIL SCADA captures of relevant electrical variables of the three converters in the MIL tests.

IV. PCS prototype hardware, control, supervision and experimental testbench

Following the simulations, the HESS PCS prototype design was validated through experimental testing with a scaled-down prototype. In this setup, the HIL404 device operated as the control platform. Figure 11 shows the simplified electrical schematic of the experimental test setup, including the PCS prototype, the voltage and current sensors for the converter closed-loop controls and safety protections, the MOSFET gate drivers, the HIL404 device, and the test-bench dc power supplies and ac grid.

One important point to note in Figure 11 is that the HIL404 device provides the control (PWM) signals to the MOSFET gate drivers, as it does not have gate drivers of its own. When connecting external circuitry to the HIL device, it is important to follow the [Safety Guidelines provided by Typhoon HIL](#) and to ensure that the appropriate safety measures are in place.

Figure 11. Electrical schematic of the PCS prototype and test bench, showing the main components: Power devices, sensors, HIL404 device, and power supplies.

Hardware implementation

The PCS prototype was built with custom-made printed-circuit boards (PCBs), which integrated and electrically connected the components according to the electrical schematics of Figure 3 and Figure 5. Figure 12 shows the PCBs and PCS components. The DAB HF transformers were placed outside of the PCBs due to its large dimensions and were connected using cables and connectors to the PCBs. The HV dc-link HF capacitors were distributed between the dc-ac converter PCB and HV-side DAB converter PCBs. Lastly, cables and connectors were employed to interconnect the PCBs and connect the system to the HIL404 device (not shown in Figure 12).

To ensure the appropriate protection, the design of the converter PCBs and the connection interfaces of the gate drivers and sensors to the control platform were planned to reduce the current-loop stray inductances and to provide electromagnetic interference (EMI) immunity, in order to ensure a reliable operation of the PCS. Additionally, the switching signals sent to the drivers were sent using differential voltage pair, to increase immunity to EMI.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. PCS prototype, showing the components assembled on the PCBs. (a) eCAD 3D view of the design. (b) Real implementation.

Control implementation

The PCS control was implemented using a HIL404 device, programmed using the model-based development approach in Schematic Editor, and employing the Signal Processing library of components. The HIL404 unit allows for high-frequency PWM output signals, used as control inputs for the MOSFET gate drivers and fast-sampling analog inputs to capture the current and voltage sensor values. Figure 13 shows the control subsystems and the dc-ac converter control in detail. Notice how, in contrast to Figure 9, Figure 13 features *PWM Modulator* blocks to implement the modulator for each dc-ac converter leg.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. PCS control program implemented in Schematic Editor. (a) Subsystems overview. (b) dc-ac converter control subsystem in detail.

A state machine was also programmed to safely manage the start and stop of the PCS converters. The state machine implemented a sequence consisting of the arming of the system, which connected the PCS to the dc supplies and the grid and then the individual turns on of the dc-dc and dc-ac converters. Analogously, it implemented a sequence for a safe turn off. Moreover, it also took care of bringing the system to a safe stop when an emergency or alarm was detected; e.g., the emergency button is pressed, an excessive phase current or a dc-link voltage is detected, etc. Figure 14 shows the state-machine implementation in Typhoon HIL Schematic Editor. This implementation primarily consists of C function blocks, which enable the implementation of arbitrary functions using the C programming language.

Figure 14. Block diagram of the state machine for the managing of the PCS start and stop sequence. Implemented in Schematic Editor.

Additionally, a human-machine interface (HMI) was programmed with the HIL SCADA tool, which is also a part of the Typhoon HIL Control Center software toolchain, for control and supervision duties. The HMI allowed the user to manage the converters start-stop sequence through the state machine, input the control reference values and parameters, and monitor the system status and signals. Figure 15 shows a screenshot of the HMI in operation.

Figure 15. View of the PCS HMI designed with HIL SCADA tool.

Experimental testbench

A picture of the experimental test bench is shown in Figure 16 and its simplified electrical schematic is the shown previously in Figure 11. The setup consisted of the PCS prototype, the HIL404 device, two dc-power supplies working as voltage sources and acting as the LTO and AORF batteries, a grid-connected autotransformer with variable voltage adjustment (not shown in the picture), and auxiliary power supplies for the sensors and fans.

Figure 16. Picture of the experimental test bench, indicating the different elements.

V. Experimental test results and comparison with expected performance

This section details the performed experimental tests and reports the obtained results. The conclusions derived from the comparison allowed to validate the PCS prototype and to demonstrate the feasibility of the optimum HESS conversion architecture and power converter designs. Due to limitations on the available instrumentation equipment, a reduced number of performance figures were obtained from the experimental tests.

The experimental tests consisted in operating the PCS prototype at the nominal operating point (OPN) for 10 min.; i.e., until the steady-state temperatures are reached. The dc sources voltage and the autotransformer line output voltage were set to those of the nominal operation point. Table 1 lists the closed-loop control setpoints for the DAB-LTO and DAB-AORF converters. These input-current setpoints are set such that the nominal active power is delivered to the grid.

Table 1. Closed-loop control setpoint values.

Controlled variable	Setpoint value
$I_{LV,LTO}^*$	16.2 A
$I_{LV,AORF}^*$	20.1 A

Experimental test results

Table 2 shows the values measured for the dc voltage and current variables in comparison to the expected values, and the input and output power of each converter and the whole PCS. Measured values are in the ballpark of the expected ones, thus proving the correct operation of the PCS prototype, HIL404 device, and the implemented control schemes.

Table 2. Measured electrical variables in the experimental tests and its expected values.

Conversion step	Parameters		Measured values	Expected values
DAB-LTO	$P_{DAB,LTO}$	DAB-LTO nominal power	3.4 kW	3.4 kW
	$I_{LV,LTO}$	LTO battery output current	16.2 A	16.2 A
	V_{LTO}	LTO LV-side dc-link voltage	210 V	210 V
	$f_{s,DAB-LTO}$	Switching frequency	20 kHz	
DAB-AORF	$P_{DAB,AORF}$	DAB-AORF nominal power	0.6 kW	0.6 kW
	$I_{LV,AORF}$	AORF battery output current	20.1 A	20.1 A
	V_{AORF}	AORF LV-side dc-link voltage	31.9 V	32 V
	$f_{s,DAB-AORF}$	Switching frequency	20 kHz	
dc-ac	$S_{nom,dc-ac}$	dc-ac nominal power	3.9 kVA	4 kVA
	V_{HV}	HV voltage	510 V	510 V
	V_{grid}	Grid phase rms voltage	149.5 V	150 V
	$f_{s,dc-ac}$	Switching frequency	10 kHz	

Besides, Figure 17 shows the ac current and voltage waveforms listed in Table 2 captured with oscilloscopes. The DAB waveform at both converters show the expected evolution, with the exception of the $i_{L,LTO}$ and $i_{L,AORF}$, which present a delay of approximately 30° due to the limited current probe bandwidth. The regulation of the dc-link voltage (v_{HV}) performs as desired, with less than 1% voltage ripple.

Figure 17. Oscilloscope captures of relevant electrical variables of the three converters in the experimental tests. Waveform v_{HV} in the top picture presents an offset of 400 V.

VI. Conclusion: A smooth and reliable transition from simulation to test

The development and validation of the HYBRIS project's HESS demonstrates the effectiveness of a carefully designed PCS in advancing energy storage technologies. The optimized PCS, combining DAB converters for LTO and AORF with a three-phase two-level dc-ac converter, achieved a balance between efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and operational flexibility.

In HYBRIS, Typhoon HIL solutions were crucial for IREC's researchers throughout all stages of the PCS prototype development. By using Typhoon HIL, the control loops could be tested and refined before employing them on the final hardware. This process significantly reduced development risks, as the exact same code be directly applied to the experimental tests with minimal additions.

After comparing the MIL simulation results in Figure 10 with the experimental tests in Figure 17, the MIL simulations closely align with the results obtained from the PCS prototype. In this regard, the simulations accurately capture both DAB and dc-ac converter waveform evolution and stability.

Overall, the successful validation of the PCS prototype highlights the effectiveness of MIL simulations in accurately portraying real hardware. By employing MIL, control strategies were thoroughly verified before experimental implementation, reducing development risks and ensuring a seamless transition in power converters prototyping.

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